

Research article

AWARENESS OF STAFF NURSES IN CLINICAL RESEARCH: A STUDY FROM YASHODA HOSPITAL

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ABSTRACT

Clinical research has play vital role in new treatment and to enhance the quality of patient's care. Nowadays in private and government medical institutions or hospital were conducting clinical research. Nurses are major role in clinical research especially in-patient wards. To investigate clinical research terminology awareness survey in our hospital staff nurses. This study 300 in ward nurses were participated survey at Yashoda Hospitals Hyderabad, and based of work experience nurses were trichotomized, trainee nurse, <3 years, and >3 years. All nurses were received objective type questionnaires with two-point scales. Among the 400 nurses at Yashoda Hospital, 300 (75%) nurses were responded to the survey questionnaires. In India, clinical trials are regulating by Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO), and local institutional ethics committee. The participations nurses 65(21.6%) were trainee nurses 100(33.3%) were < 3 years and 135(45%) were >3 years experiences nurses. Approximately 50-65% of nurses were respondents aware of clinical research terminology. In clinical research terminology, most respondents were aware of nurse's major role in clinical trials, and informed consent, but 40% were aware of Good Clinical Practice (GCP). We found >3 years experiences nurses were significantly aware of all clinical research terminology compared to trainee. Our findings suggest that staff nurses have limited knowledge on clinical research terminology and to make improve knowledge in clinical research by nursing education program.

Keywords: Nurses, awareness clinical research, ethics committee, Yashoda hospital

Abbreviations

CDSCO/DCGI: Central Drugs Standard Control Organization/Drugs Controller General of India

CTRI: Clinical Trials Registry- India

GCP: Good Clinical Practice

ICF: Inform consent form

ICMR: Indian Council of Medical Research

ISC: Institutional Scientific Committee

SPSS: Statistical Package for the Social Sciences

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Email: rsbhandaru@gmail.com**DOI:** xxx-xxxx-xxxx-xxxx**INTRODUCTION**

Clinical research is playing major role in health care industry, and in accordance with local regulators. Its development of new treatment and in the quality of patient life care ¹. The possibility of new treatment options or the advancement of existing treatments can be accomplished by clinical research only. The achievement of clinical research by good clinical research team like principal investigator, coordinators, and study staff nurse. Although it is essential for clinical research nurses have led of public awareness during the COVID-19 pandemic time. Clinical research nurse is one of the important members of this multidisciplinary team. Other challenges in clinical research include increasing difficulty of clinical research studies and challenging study populations. The role and responsibilities of nurses in clinical research it may be varied according to the types of clinical trials and indication of disease ². Clinical research nursing is the particular practice of specialized nursing focused on keeping balance between patient care of the trial participant and dependability to the research protocol ³.

Nurses are main pillar of Indian healthcare system and representing 30% of the entire health workforce. In India studies have showed very less performing clinical trials compared to western countries other Asian countries like Japan and Chain ⁴. India subcontinent have around 20% of the global disease burden and 18% accountability of the world population, but < 2% of globally clinical trials performed.⁵ In hospitals and medical institutions,

clinical nurses, working as ward-based clinical research especially oncology neurology, critical care and engaged in clinical research particularly nursing team. Studies have incriminated clinical research nurses having less clinical research terminology in India, compared to western part 4. The current study to investigate awareness survey of clinical research terminology our staff nurses. Very limited studies have available on this topic from India.

2. Material and Methods

This is an observational prospective study; in this study 300 staff nurses were contributed. This study was carryout at Yashoda Hospital, Hyderabad South India, Yashoda hospital is a tertiary care center and teaching hospital in South India, study period was from March 2020 to February 2022, and this study was approved by Institutional Scientific Committee (ISC).

Out of 500 staff nurses 300 nurses were voluntarily participated, all nurses were completed graduation of nursing. Based on staff nurses work experiences, we were trichotomized (trainee nurses < 3 years and ≥ 3years).

We used two-point scales questionnaires to survey the knowledge of clinical research. The questionnaire had 7 domains. The first domain contained 7 items, in order to determine the terminology of clinical research of the nurses participating in this research such as aware of clinical trials, ethics committee, Central Drugs Standard Control Organization/Drugs Controller General of India (CDSCO/DCGI), Good clinical practice (GCP) guidelines, and Indian Council of Medical Research(ICMR).The second domain had 6 items regarding basic knowledge of clinical trial phase I to Phase IV, investigator-initiated trial and academic research. Third domain was knowledge of ethics committee and containing 4 items like hospital ethics committee, ethics committee permission required for clinical trials conducting in hospital, patient consent is required for clinical trial and patient consent form approved by ethics committee. Fourth domain was knowledge of CDSCO/DCGI and its having 3 items such as DCGI/CDSCO approval for clinical trials conducting in hospital, new drugs approved by DCGI/CDSCO and clinical trial drug as investigational drug, fifth domain was GCP guidelines and related to GCP

certificate required for clinical trials sixth domain had knowledge of ICMR and regarding 3 items and containing ICMR is a government agency, ICMR ethical guidelines and Clinical Trials Registry- India(CTRI), and last domain was role of nurses in clinical trials and having 10 items clinical trials nursing should be considered as a profession, investigational drug, clinical trials improve the quality of patient care, clinical trial is trustworthy, nurses are theoretical to have more knowledge in clinical research, clinical research is beneficial for the society, pregnant women and childbearing/breastfeeding women not participated in clinical trials, patient participants in clinical trial safety is important, patients must sign the Informed consent form(ICF) before participating in a clinical trial, and any adverse reaction hospitalization occurs during clinical trial the treatment cost covered by the sponsor.

2.1 Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed by SPSS 16.0 (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences, SPSS Inc statistical package Chicago IL USA). Continuous variables were presented in titer of mean and \pm standard deviation was calculated. Chi-square test was applied to study the difference between two groups (aware vs not aware). All tests were two-sided and $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant.

3. Results

Out of 300 staff nurses, male nurses were 4(1.3%), female nurses were 296(98.6%), below 25 years age group nurses were 120(40%), and above 26 years age group were 180(60%).Based on nurse's work experiences trainee nurses were 65(21.6%), <3 years experiences were 100(33.3%), >3 years experiences were 135(45%) (Table 1).

In table 2 showed, in clinical terminology domain 65% had aware of clinical trials, 63.3% had nurse's major role in clinical trials, 54.6 %had aware of CDSCO/DCGI and 50% had aware of ethics committee. Knowledge of clinical trial domain 51.3% had aware of phase IV clinical trials and 50% had aware of Phase III clinical trials. Knowledge of ethics committee domain 53.3% had patient consent is required for clinical trial, 52.3% had aware of ethics committee permission and 51.3% had aware of in

our hospital having ethics committee. Knowledge of CDSCO/DCGI domain 56.6% had aware of DCGI/CDSCO approval required for clinical trials conducting in hospital, 56.3% had aware of all drugs approved by DCGI/CDSCO. Knowledge of GCP guidelines domain 40% had aware of GCP. Knowledge of ICMR domain 54.6% had aware of ICMR is a government agency. Role of nurses in clinical trials domain 58.3% had aware of pregnant women and childbearing/ breastfeeding women not participated in clinical trials, 56% had aware of clinical research is beneficial for the society, 55% had aware of nurses are theoretical to have more knowledge in clinical research, 52.6% had aware of clinical trials improve the quality of patient care, 50.6% had aware of patient participants in clinical trial safety is important, and 50% had aware of patients must sign the Informed consent form (ICF) before participating in a clinical trial.

Table 3 showed >3-year work experience staff nurses were significantly aware of clinical research terminology ($p=0.02$), aware of clinical trials ($p=0.03$) aware of ethics committee ($p=0.04$), aware of GCP guidelines, aware of ICMR ($p=0.04$) and aware of nurse's major role in clinical trials ($p=0.03$).

4. Discussion

The present study we found staff nurses awareness of clinical research has multiple combination factors were involved. These combinations of factors and staff nurses focus on self-leadership and ethics has the potential to contribute to the communications on challenges in clinical research and should be measured by policy makers and administrative leads.

In our study, we noted 98.6% have female nurses some other studies have showed Aksoy et al 97%1, Yanagawa et al 95.4% 6, Pillai et al 62.1% 4. We found 40% under 25 years age group, 60% above 26 years age group, some other studies have showed 51% <35 years age group by Aksoy et al 1, <30 years 41% Yanagawa et al 6. We noted, our staff nurse work experience 33.3% of <5 years working, trainee nurse similar findings noted by Pillai et al 50% 4, and Yanagawa et al 31% 6.

4.1 Terminology of Clinical Research

In current study, we found 65% staff nurse have awareness clinical research terminology, some other

studies have noted 90% of awareness 6. The present study, we compared awareness in various subgroups participating staff nurses 40% having GCP guidelines. These findings may influence nurses' knowledge. It required regular continues education programs in clinical research. Mac Learn et al showed in his study to developed a research curriculum based on clinical research 7. In our study we found significant with >3.1 years experiences staff nurses compared to trainee nurses ($p=0.02$), these findings were advocated by Yanagawa et al 6.

4.2 Knowledge of clinical trials

The present study we noted our staff nurse aware of clinical trials 49%. Some other studies have showed higher awareness 4,6. In our study we found more aware phase iv clinical trial compared to other phases trails our finding supported by others 1. Yanagawa et al showed in his study significantly positive correlation with clinical trial various phases 6. Pillai et al noted in his study 90% aware clinical trial in various phases 4. The current study showed significant with >3.1 years experiences staff nurses compared to trainee nurses ($p=0.03$) these findings were supported by others 2,4.

4.3 Knowledge of ethics committee

In our study we established 50% staff nurses aware of institutional ethic committee, Aksoy et al showed in his study 85% aware of staff nurse 1. Yanagawa et al showed 75.5% have aware of ethics committee 6, in our study, we noted 50% staff nurse aware of consent form is required for participated in clinical research, some other studies have showed more than 70% aware of consent form required 1,4,6. The present study established significant with >3.1 years experiences staff nurses compared to trainee nurses ($p=0.04$), these findings were supported by others 1,5.

4.4 Knowledge of CDSCO/DCGI

The current study, we found 54% aware of Indian regulatory bodies, Pillai et al showed 90% aware of CDSCO/DCGI 4. Yanagawa et al noted more than 90% aware regulatory bodies in Japan 6. In our study less aware due not much more experience in clinical research. Our findings advocated by Sharma et al 50% 8. Few studies have established experiences staff nurses (more than 3 years) have aware the Indian regulatory bodies 4.

4.5 Knowledge of GCP guidelines

We noted, our study 43.3% aware of GCP, similar findings showed by Aksoy et al 39% 1, some other studies showed 90% staff nurse aware of GCP 4, these variations due lack of knowledge of GCP. Tannir et al. highlighted nurses are required GCP training programme for regularly 9. Goel et al emphasized continues educational intervention required for GCP nurses and doctors, the training program its help to increase their knowledge and awareness about techniques and principles of clinical research 10. Dhodi et al also mentioned that the number of GCP training programmers conducted increase credibility of clinical trials 2, another study showed one day GCP training workshop for nurses its helpful their work quality 11, few studies have showed in government hospitals also required training programme 12. In our study GCP experience nurses have significantly aware of GCP guidelines compared trainee nurses ($p=0.02$), these findings advocated others 4,8,10.

4.6 Knowledge of ICMR

In our study, we found 46.6% staff nurses aware of ICMR and their guidelines for clinical research some other studies have showed similar findings 4, 11. Sharma et al showed in his study more 50% nurses aware of ICMR guidelines 8. In our study we noted experiences nurses have significantly knowledge ICMR guidelines compared to trainee nurses ($p=0.04$).

4.7 Role of nurses in Clinical research

The current study we established staff nurses has 45% aware of their role in clinical research. Flocke et al showed in his study staff nurses having role of nurse in clinical research 13. Alahmad et al showed in study 50% aware their role in clinical research 14. Mueller examines the social and historical development of nurses' roles in clinical research and argues that nurses need to demonstrate the unique skills and knowledge that they can offer to the role 15. The present study, we found significant awareness clinical research compared to trainee nurses ($p=0.03$). However few studies have showed nurses' lack of knowledge and their role in clinical researches 7, 16, 17.

4.8 Fit polls of study

In our study have few limitations, the first one nurses sample size is less, second few nurses were trines, third one is our few domains in Indian subcontinent related questionnaires, these questionnaires we were unable to comparison in western literature. The strength of our study few questionnaires results were resembled to western results. Our samples were analyzed chi-square test for three groups.

5. Conclusions

In our study we established staff nurses having limited knowledge on clinical research terminology, and also noted few of the nurses have aware of the clinical research terminology most of the trainee nurses doesn't have aware of the clinical research terminology. Staff nurses require training workshops like GCP, ICMR guidelines CDSCO act workshops seminars, to make improve knowledge in clinical research by nursing education program.

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7. Conflict of Interest and disclosures

All authors declared no conflict of interest and disclosures we nil.

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Table 1: Baseline characters

Parameters	Number (n=300)
Male nurse	4(1.3%)
Female nurse	296(98.6%)
Age group (≤ 25 years)	120(40%)
Age group (≥ 26 years)	180(60%)
Trainee nurse	65(21.6%)
<3 years experiences	100(33.3%)
>3 years experiences	135(45%)

Table 2: Comparison of various domains with aware vs not aware

Two-point scales questioner survey	Aware	Not aware
Terminology of Clinical Research		
Are you aware of clinical trials	195(65%)	105(35%)
Are you aware of ethics committee	150(50%)	150(50%)
Are you aware of CDSCO/DCGI	164(54.6%)	136(45.4%)
Are you aware of GCP guidelines	120(40%)	180(60%)
Are you aware of ICMR	140(46.6%)	160(53.4%)
Are you aware of nurse's major role in Clinical trials	190(63.3%)	110(36.7%)

Are you aware of Principal Investigator	147(49%)	153(51%)
Knowledge of clinical trials		
Are you aware of Phase I clinical trials	120(40%)	180(60%)
Are you aware of Phase II clinical trials	140(46.6%)	160(53.4%)
Are you aware of Phase III clinical trials	150(50%)	150(50%)
Are you aware of Phase IV clinical trials	154(51.3%)	146(48.7%)
Are you aware of investigator-initiated trial	138(46%)	162(54%)
Are you aware of academic research	144(48%)	156(52%)
Knowledge of ethics committee		
Are you aware of in our hospital having ethics committee	154(51.3%)	146(48.7%)
Are you aware of ethics committee permission required for clinical trials conducting in hospital	157(52.3%)	143(47.7%)
Are you aware of patient consent is required for clinical trial	160(53.3%)	140(46.7%)
Are you aware of the Patient consent form approved by ethics committee	130(43.3%)	170(56.7%)
Knowledge of CDSCO/DCGI		
Are you aware of DCGI/CDSCO approval required for clinical trials conducting in hospital	152(56.6%)	148(43.4%)
Are you aware of all drugs approved by DCGI/CDSCO	169(56.3%)	131(43.7%)
Are you aware of clinical trial drug as investigational drug	148(49.3%)	152(50.6%)
Knowledge of GCP guidelines		
Are you aware of Good clinical practice (GCP)	165(55%)	135(45%)
Are you aware of GCP certificate required for clinical trials	120(40%)	180(60%)
Knowledge of ICMR		

Are you aware of ICMR is a government agency	164(54.6%)	136(45.4%)
Are you aware of ICMR ethical guidelines	120(40%)	180(60%)
Are you aware of CTRI	110(36.6%)	190(64.6%)
Role of nurses in Clinical trials		
Are you aware of clinical trials nursing should be considered as a profession	165(55%)	135(45%)
Are you aware of investigational drug	148(49.3%)	152(50.7%)
Are you aware of clinical trials improve the quality of patient care	158(52.6%)	142(47.4%)
Are you aware of Clinical trial is trustworthy	142(47.3%)	152(52.7%)
Are you aware of nurses are theoretical to have more knowledge in clinical research	165(55%)	135(45%)
Are you aware of Clinical research is beneficial for the society	168(56%)	132(44%)
Are you aware of pregnant women and childbearing/ breastfeeding women not participated in clinical trials	175(58.3%)	125(41.7%)
Are you aware of patient participants in clinical trial safety is important	152(50.6%)	148(49.4%)
Are you aware of patients must sign the Informed consent form before participating in a clinical trial	150(50%)	150(50%)
Are you aware of if any adverse reaction occurs during clinical trial the treatment cost covered by the sponsor	149(49.6%)	151(50.4%)

CDSCO/DCGI: Central Drugs Standard Control Organization/Drugs Controller General of India
CTRI: Clinical Trials Registry- India, GCP: Good Clinical Practice, ICMR: Indian Council of Medical Research

Table 3: Comparison of various domains with trainee nurses and experience nurses

Domains	Trainee Nurses (n=65)	≤ 3 years experience (n=100)	≥ 3.1 years Experience (n=135)	p value
Aware of clinical research terminology	20(30%)	60(60%)*	115(85.1%)	0.02
Are you aware of clinical trials	15(23%)	65(65%)*	125(92.5%)	0.03
Are you aware of ethics committee	10(15.3%)	50(50%)*	90(60.6%)	0.04
Are you aware of CDSCO/DCGI	25(38.4%)	67(67%)	72(53.3%)	0.07
Are you aware of GCP guidelines	4(6.1%)	50(50%)*	76(56.2%)	0.02
Are you aware of ICMR	18(27.6%)	52(52%)*	70(50%)	0.04
Are you aware of nurse's major role in Clinical trials	28(43%)	64(64%)*	119(88.1%)	0.03

* No significant between <3 years and >3years work experience

CDSCO/DCGI: Central Drugs Standard Control Organization/Drugs Controller General of India

GCP: Good Clinical Practice, ICMR: Indian Council of Medical Research